

Horizon 2020 TWEETHER

Travelling wave tube based w-band wireless networks with high data rate distribution, spectrum & energy efficiency

Project no: 644678

Project acronym: **TWEETHER**

Project title: **Travelling wave tube based w-band wireless networks with high data rate distribution, spectrum & energy efficiency**

WP7.

Deliverable D7.2: Website of Tweether

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Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The TWEETHER project website is available at www.tweether.eu since March, 2015.

This report describes the website sections and provides an overview of its contents. In particular, the website has a public part to facilitate the spread of project's information to different stakeholders, a private part, accessible only by consortium members, dedicated to information exchange between partners and a reserved area for the EU Commission.

1. INTRODUCTION

The TWEETHER website has a public area, targeting external audience to the consortium, and an internal, password protected area.

The TWEETHER public website is the core element of the project's dissemination strategy and is intended to provide a vision of the project and general information about the main activities and results achieved with the objective to:

- Raise awareness about the project activities
- Facilitate the diffusion of the project's results
- Promote their industrial exploitation

On the other hand, the internal area is reserved to the TWEETHER partners for efficient and rapid communication and for sharing files and information.

2. GENERAL STRUCTURE OF THE WEBSITE

The URL of the website is <http://www.tweether.eu> and is online since March, 2015. The website is hosted and maintained by UPV and will be updated regularly with scientific results, findings and achievements.

The TWEETHER public area is composed of a home page, that shortly introduces the project and where the user can find the latest news and upcoming events, and a menu structured according to the following navigation points:

- About,
- Technology,
- Dissemination,
- News & Events
- Contact.

A screenshot of the website home page is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. TWEETHER website

A brief description of each website section is given below.

- **Section “About”.** In this section a summary of the TWEETHER project, including the context and the main objectives to be addressed, is provided. Moreover, it presents the institutions as well as organizations involved in the project and gives a short description of the work plan with information about the specific objectives, and leaders of each work package. Fig. 2 shows a screenshot of the Project Description Section.

Fig. 2. Project Description

- **Section “Technology”**. This section introduces the main technological challenges to be faced by the project to set a milestone in millimetre wave technology. This section will be updated during the lifetime of the project with the main technological achievement obtained. Fig. 3 shows the Technology section.

Fig. 3. TWEETHER Technology

- **Section “Dissemination”**. This section records all the research papers, related to the project, published by partners on scientific journals and conference proceedings. Also, public deliverables released during the project are listed in the section Public Deliverables. On the other hand, newsletters and other dissemination material will be posted here to be downloaded for TWEETHER website users.

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Fig. 4. Publications Section

- **Section “News & Events”**. This page shows news, press releases and upcoming events related to TWEETHER. For example, press releases of the project and a list of conferences or workshops dedicated to particular sub-domains of the project goals will be announced in this section.

Fig. 5. News Section

- **Section “Contact”**. This section provides the contact details of the TWEETHER Coordinator in case the website users want to get further information about the project.

Apart from the navigation points explained before, a link to the **TWEETHER collaborative platform** used for internal communication is available at the bottom of the home page. This private Deliverable D7.2

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area is password-protected and its access is only allowed to project partners. A login and a password have already been provided to each TWEETHER member.

This platform is based on Thales “external –Team-on-Line” (eToL) platform. The objective of this platform is to have a secure and private place to share documents between partners and a special section, in the form of forum, to have discussion about issues arising from the different work packages. This platform will also be used to keep working versions of documents such as on-going version of reports and deliverables and to have a repository of deliverables, meeting minutes and all documents relevant to the project.

Additionally, a “Reviewers area” to allow file exchange with the project officer and the reviewers has been established. A login and a password will be provided shortly. Fig. 6 shows the Reviewers Area.

The image shows the login interface for the TWEETHER REVIEWERS AREA. At the top, the logo 'tweether' is displayed in a teal, lowercase font with a wavy underline, followed by 'REVIEWERS AREA' in a smaller, uppercase font. Below the logo, there are two input fields: one for 'Username' and one for 'Password'. A teal button labeled 'Sign in' is positioned below the password field.

Fig. 6. Reviewers Area

Finally, the home page has also links to Twitter and LinkedIn accounts of the project (Fig. 7 and Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. Twitter of the project

Fig. 8. LinkedIn group for TWEETHER

3. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE UPGRADES

The public website and private area for the TWEETHER project have been set up. While the public website represents the key element of the project's dissemination strategy, the private area acts as repository of final and ongoing versions of documents, providing a way to share private information between the partners of the project.

The website provides a basic set of information about the project and will be regularly updated in order to better satisfy possible new dissemination requirements emerging during the project's evolution. Additionally, new ways to enhance the dissemination and spreading of TWEETHER outcomes will be evaluated. For example, a web tracker providing web statistics will be used to assess the website visibility and make website improvements based on this information.